
Parental Influence and Adolescent Bonding: A Study of Parent-Child Relationship among Secondary School Students in Nainital District

Deepika Pant Pandey

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Amrapali University, Haldwani, Uttarakhand

deepikapantpandey@gmail.com

Mayank Pandey

Assistant Professor, Department of Biotechnology, Sir J.C. Bose Technical Campus, Bhimtal, Kumaun

University, Uttarakhand, pandeymayank80@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to examine the status of parent-child relationships among adolescents with respect to their gender, age, locality, parental occupation, and education. Employing the descriptive survey method, the study was conducted in four selected blocks—Haldwani, Kotabagh, Ramgarh, and Bhimtal—out of the total eight administrative blocks of Nainital district, Uttarakhand. A sample of secondary school students was selected using the simple random sampling technique to ensure objectivity and representativeness. The study provides valuable insights into how socio-demographic factors influence the quality of the parent-child relationship during adolescence. Findings of the research may assist educators, counselors, and parents in fostering stronger bonds and supportive environments for adolescents' emotional and social development.

Introduction:

It is unanimously recognized that every human being is a product of both heredity and environment, and parents are the primary source of both. The parent-child relationship, therefore, holds

immense significance in the holistic development of an adolescent. Parents not only contribute to their child's biological makeup but also play a foundational role in shaping behavior, attitudes, communication skills, and emotional regulation through daily interactions (Singh & Lal, 2020).

Adolescence, being a transitional phase, is marked by rapid emotional and psychological changes. During this critical stage, a strong and supportive parent-child relationship is essential for nurturing resilience, emotional security, academic motivation, and social competence. Parents act as the first educators, and through their behaviors, adolescents learn how to interact with others, manage stress, and understand themselves (Lal, 2013).

The quality of this relationship—whether healthy or unhealthy—greatly impacts the adolescent's well-being. A healthy parent-child bond is characterized by warmth, empathy, open communication, and emotional support, which foster a sense of belonging and self-worth (Perry & Szalavitz, 2006). On the contrary, neglect, poor communication, or overly authoritarian approaches can lead to stress, behavioral problems, and diminished academic performance.

In the specific socio-cultural context of the Nainital district in Uttarakhand, where family values are deeply rooted, yet modern pressures continue to rise, examining the dynamics of parent-child relationships becomes especially relevant. Factors such as parental education, socio-economic background, communication style, marital stability, and cultural beliefs significantly influence these relationships. Research shows that adolescents with strong parental bonds tend to perform better academically, exhibit fewer behavioral issues, and show improved life skills such as decision-making, emotional regulation, and social interaction (Steinberg, 2001; Maccoby & Martin, 1983).

This study aims to explore the influence of parental behavior and bonding on the development and adjustment of secondary school students in the Nainital district. Understanding these dynamics can help educators, counselors, and policymakers promote healthier home environments and more supportive family interactions for the overall well-being of adolescents.

Review of Related Studies

A significant body of research underscores the crucial role of parent-child relationships and family environments in shaping adolescents' emotional, cognitive, and social development. Studies have shown that warm, affectionate parenting reduces stress, enhances emotional well-being, and fosters

creativity. For instance, Anagha and Sreevalsan (2021) found that supportive parent-child bonds boost adolescents' confidence and academic performance, while Perry (2021) highlighted the importance of parental involvement in youth programs for emotional and academic growth.

Nurturing behaviors such as acceptance and autonomy positively influence emotional competence and creativity, with mothers typically showing more acceptance than fathers (Jankowski & Gralowski, 2022). Conversely, negative parenting behaviors, including neglect, can harm adolescents' adjustment and development. Additionally, a stable family environment, including strong communication, is linked to better decision-making, critical thinking, and social skills (Singh & Lal, 2022; Preety & Rani, 2023).

Supportive parenting also encourages social-emotional competencies, fosters creativity, and reduces risky behaviors (Bao et al., 2023; He et al., 2024). Furthermore, family factors like socioeconomic background and parental education contribute to cognitive and emotional development (Li et al., 2023). Overall, these studies emphasize that positive parent-child relationships and active parental engagement are vital for adolescents' emotional well-being, academic success, and overall development.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To examine the status of parent-child relationships among secondary school students in Nainital district.
2. To analyze the impact of gender on the quality of parent-child relationships.
3. To explore the influence of age on the dynamics of parent-child bonding.
4. To study the effect of locality (urban vs. rural) on the nature of parent-child relationships.
5. To assess the role of parental occupation in shaping parent-child relationships.
6. To investigate how parental education level influences the strength and quality of parent-child relationships.

Research method:

The present study employed the **descriptive survey method** to investigate the parent-child relationship among secondary school students.

Sampling Technique and Sample

A combination of **purposive sampling** and **simple random sampling** techniques was used for selecting the sample. Firstly, out of the **8 blocks** in the **Nainital district**, **4 blocks** were selected using the **lottery method**, ensuring a fair and unbiased selection process. Following this, **23 secondary schools**

were selected from a total of **106 schools** using the **purposive sampling technique**. The selection of schools was based on factors such as accessibility, student enrollment, and availability of required data. From these 23 schools, a total of 800 students from classes 9 and 10 were selected as respondents using the simple random sampling technique. Within each selected school, students were asked to line up and were given the freedom to choose any number of their choice. Students who selected odd numbers (1, 3, 5, 7, etc.) were included in the sample, ensuring random selection.

Research Tool

The tool used for data collection was the **Parent-Child Relationship Scale (PCRS)** developed by **Dr. Nalini Rao (2016)**. This standardized scale assesses the quality of the parent-child relationship across **ten dimensions**: protecting, symbolic punishment, symbolic reward, object punishment, object reward, indifferent, loving, neglecting, rejecting, and controlling. The scale provided a detailed measure of students' perceptions of their relationships with both parents.

Procedure for Data Collection

After the selection of schools and respondents, necessary permissions were obtained from the school authorities to conduct the survey. The researcher personally visited each of the **23 selected secondary schools** across the **4 identified blocks** of Nainital district. Students from **classes 9 and 10** were assembled, and the purpose of the study was explained to them. The importance of honest and unbiased responses was emphasized, and confidentiality was assured. The respondents were guided on how to fill out the scale correctly. Ample time was provided to ensure thoughtful and complete responses. The researcher ensured that a quiet and comfortable environment was maintained during the data collection process.

Findings and discussion:

1, Status of Parent-Child Relationship among Secondary School Students in Nainital district

To examine the parent-child relationship among secondary school students, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation of the total sample (n=800) in relation to mother scores, father scores and overall parent scores were calculated.

Table 1: Mean, and Standard deviation of Parent-child Relationship among Secondary School Students (N=800)

S.N.	Dimensions of Parent-Child Relationship		Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Protecting	Father	32.13	6.66
		Mother	33.61	7.23
2	Symbolic Punishment	Father	26.68	4.97
		Mother	27.32	4.89
3	Rejecting	Father	22.96	6.21
		Mother	23.15	6.27
4	Object Punishment	Father	23.10	6.38
		Mother	23.38	6.32
5	Demanding	Father	25.01	5.38
		Mother	25.09	5.39
6	Indifferent	Father	24.70	5.11
		Mother	25.78	4.77
7	Symbolic Reward	Father	30.06	5.40
		Mother	30.25	5.52
8	Loving	Father	30.93	5.55
		Mother	31.42	5.68
9	Object Reward	Father	27.83	5.66
		Mother	28.39	5.73
10	Neglecting	Father	23.01	6.14
		Mother	23.05	6.08
11	Father -child relationship		266.39	26.79
12	Mother-child relationship		271.45	26.59
13	Overall Parent -child relationship		269.16	25.10

Fig.1 Mean value of Father (left) and Mother (right) for various dimensions of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Fig.2 Mean value of Father-child relationship, Mother-child relationship and Overall parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Table 1 and Figure 1 & 2 shows the mean scores for various dimensions of parent-child relationship, mother-child relationship, father-child relationship, and overall parent-child relationship among secondary school students. The mother-child relationship has a mean score of 271.45 ± 26.59 , while the

father-child relationship has a mean score of 266.39 ± 26.79 . The overall mean for the parent-child relationship is 269.16 ± 25.10 . The table also details the mean scores for various dimensions of the parent-child relationship. For the mother, the mean scores for protecting (33.61), symbolic punishment (27.32), rejecting (23.15), indifferent (25.78), loving (31.43), and object reward (28.39) were higher than those for the father. On the other hand, the mean scores for demanding, neglecting, object punishment and symbolic reward are similar for both parents.

The analyzed data indicated that the mother-child relationship is perceived slightly more positively than the father-child relationship, with higher mean scores in several dimensions. Both relationships showed moderate consistency in respondents' perceptions, with similar variability around the mean. Overall, mothers were viewed more strongly in both positive and negative aspects, while fathers were perceived similarly in demanding, neglecting, and punishment dimensions.

Table 2 Frequency distribution and Percentage of parent-child relationship among secondary school students (N=800)

Level of relationship	Father-Child Relationship Frequency(Percentage)	Mother-Child Relationship Frequency(Percentage)	Parent-Child Relationship Frequency(Percentage)
Good	111 (13.87%)	133 (16.6%)	109 (13.0%)
Average	525 (65.62%)	568 (71.0%)	573 (72%)
Poor	164 (20.51%)	99 (12.4%)	118(15%)
Total	800	800	800

Figure 3 Status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Table 2 and Figure 3 shows that only 13.87% (N=111) of students reported good father-child relationship, while the majority, 65.62% (N=525), had an average father-child relationship, and 20.51% (N=164) had a low father-child relationship. Regarding the mother-child relationship, 71.0% (N=568) of students reported an average relationship, 16.6% (N=133) had a good relationship, and 12.4% (N=99) had a low relationship. Overall, the results indicate that only 13.0% (N=109) of secondary students experienced a good parent-child relationship, with 72.0% (N=573) having an average relationship, and 15.0% (N=118) reporting a low parent-child relationship.

The findings revealed that, while the majority of students maintain an average relationship with their parents, there is a significant portion who perceive their relationships as either good or low, highlighting variations in the strength of parent-child interactions among secondary school students.

Table 3 Dimension wise frequency distribution and percentage of parent-child relationship among secondary school students (N=800)

S.N.	Dimensions of Parent-child Relationship	Levels of Parent- child Relationship		
		High	Average	Low
1.	Protecting	58(7.25%)	693 (86.62%)	49(6.13%)
2	Symbolic Punishment	3(0.37%)	562(70.25%)	235 (29.38%)
3	Rejecting	40(5%)	629(78.6%)	131(16.4%)
4	Object Punishment	63(7.8%)	592 (74%)	145(18.2%)
5	Demanding	12(1.5%)	618 (77.25%)	170 (21.25%)
6	Indifferent	0 (0%)	542 (67.75%)	258 (32.25%)
7	Symbolic Reward	0(0%)	724(90.5%)	76(9.5%)
8	Loving	0(0%)	740 (92.5%)	60(7.5%)
9	Object Reward	0(0%)	658(82.25%)	142 (17.75%)
10	Neglecting	131(16.7%)	614(76.5%)	55 (6.8%)

Figure 4 Dimension wise status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

It was observed from table 3 and figure 4 that, the majority of student’s parent-child relationships across various dimensions fell within the average level category, For Protecting, Symbolic Punishment, Rejecting, Object Punishment, Demanding, Indifferent, Symbolic Reward, Loving, and Object Reward dimensions, the average levels constitute notably high percentages ranging from 67.75% to 92.5%. In Neglecting dimension a relatively higher percentage 16.7% of students experienced high level of neglectful behavior, 76.5% students experienced average level while only 6.8% of students experienced low level of neglecting behavior of parents.

The findings indicate that most secondary school students experience an average level of parent-child relationship, with higher mean scores for mother-child bonds, suggesting a stronger emotional connection with mothers. This can be attributed to the traditional caregiving role of mothers in Indian households, where they are more involved in daily tasks like meal preparation, supervising homework, and managing routines—promoting emotional closeness. In contrast, fathers, typically focused on financial responsibilities, have fewer opportunities for day-to-day interaction, limiting emotional bonding. Lamb (2010) highlights these gender-based differences in parental involvement.

Adolescence is a stage where emotional support is vital. As mothers are perceived as more empathetic and emotionally available, adolescents may feel more connected to them. Indian cultural norms and socialization further reinforce this perception, linking emotional expression more closely with mothers. These findings align with Kaur, Maheshwari, and Thapar (2015), who also observed moderate parent-child relationships among students. However, they differ from Shakila (2017), who reported stronger bonds. This variation may stem from regional, socio-economic, or cultural differences. Additionally, academic pressure, digital distractions, and reduced family time might contribute to the average relationship level. Hence, parents need to adopt more engaging and communicative approaches to strengthen their bond with adolescents.

2 Gender Wise Status of Parent-Child Relationship:

The gender of the child can influence the parent-child relationship, with parents often exhibiting different behaviors based on the child's gender. Fathers may take part in more physical play with sons and offer emotional support to daughters, while mothers might be more nurturing with daughters and promote independence in sons (Lamb, 2010; Fagot & Hagan, 1991). These gender-based differences can shape children's self-concepts and emotional development, impacting their relationship with their parents (Pleck, 2010).

Table 4 Gender wise status of parent-child relationship:

	MALE (N=400)		FEMALE (N=400)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Father-child Relationship	270.14	28.46	262.64	24.48
Mother-child Relationship	272.98	28.21	269.91	24.80
Overall Parent-child Relationship	271.80	26.93	266.53	22.86

Figure 5 Gender wise status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Table 4 and Figure 5 show that male secondary school students report slightly better relationships with both fathers (mean = 270.14) and mothers (mean = 272.98) compared to females (father = 262.64, mother = 269.91). The overall parent-child relationship score is also higher for males (271.80) than females (266.53). This trend is consistent with Toor (2018), who also found boys scoring higher than girls in mother-child relationships. Notably, male responses showed greater variability, suggesting a broader range of experiences, while female responses were more consistent.

In Uttarakhand's semi-rural context, traditional gender roles influence family interactions. Boys, viewed as future breadwinners, may receive more open communication, whereas daughters, more involved in domestic roles, may face limitations in emotional expression (Kakar, 1978; Verma & Saraswathi, 2002). Parental migration and household responsibilities in hilly regions further impact involvement. Mothers, usually present at home, nurture closer bonds, especially with sons, while fathers, engaged in external work, have limited interaction time. Regional customs and socio-economic factors shape these gender-based parenting styles (Sharma & Sharma, 2010; Singh & Kaushik, 2017). However, not all research supports these differences. Sharma (2012) found no significant gender gap, suggesting that education, awareness, and urbanization may be gradually shifting traditional parenting norms in Uttarakhand.

3. Age Wise Status of Parent-Child Relationship:

Different developmental stages demand varying levels of support, communication, and autonomy. Studies suggest that during adolescence, as children seek independence, the depth of the parent-child relationship can significantly influence their emotional well-being and behavioral outcomes (Steinberg, 2001; Smetana, 2011). In present study, statuses of parent-child relationship with respect of secondary school student's age group are categorized under two categories i.e. 12-14 year age-group and 15-17 age groups. Mean and S.D. scores of parent-child relationship with respect to their age groups are displayed in table 5 and figure 6.

Table 5 Age wise status of Parent-Child Relationship among Secondary School Students (N=800)

	Age- Group	N	Mean	S.D.
Father-child Relationship	12-14 year	344	265.20	27.08
	15-17 year	456	267.29	26.57
Mother-child Relationship	12-14 year	344	269.95	27.08
	15-17 year	456	272.57	26.19
Overall Parent-child Relationship	12-14 year	344	267.81	25.77
	15-17 year	456	270.18	24.56

Figure 6 Age wise status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Table 5 and Figure 6 show a slight improvement in parent-child relationships as students age from 12–14 to 15–17 years. Father-child relationship scores increase from 265.20 to 267.29, with stable variability (S.D. 27.08 and 26.57). Mother-child scores are higher, from 269.95 to 272.57, with a slight decline in variability (S.D. 27.08 and 26.19). Overall, the parent-child relationship mean increases from 267.81 to 270.18, with decreasing standard deviation (25.77 to 24.56), indicating growing consistency in older students' perceptions.

These findings suggest that as students grow older, their relationships with parents tend to improve slightly and become more stable. This trend may be attributed to increasing emotional maturity and a better understanding of family expectations among adolescents. As they transition into late adolescence, they often begin to value parental guidance more and communicate more effectively, leading to reduced conflict and strengthened emotional bonds (Steinberg, 2001; Laursen & Collins, 2004).

In the specific socio-cultural context of Uttarakhand, where strong family values, respect for elders, and interdependence are deeply rooted—especially in rural and semi-urban areas—this pattern becomes even more pronounced. Many families in the region continue to live in joint or extended setups, where frequent and meaningful parent-child interactions are common. These cultural factors likely contribute to the steady improvement in relationship quality observed with age.

Moreover, adolescents in the 15–17 year age group in Uttarakhand often take on greater academic and household responsibilities, which may lead to increased trust and open communication between parents and children. In the hilly and often close-knit communities of the region, where external social influences might be limited, the family continues to serve as the primary source of emotional and moral support. This can reinforce the stability and consistency of parent-child relationships.

The slightly higher scores in mother-child relationships across both age groups may reflect the traditional caregiving role of mothers in Uttarakhand's households. Mothers often serve as the primary emotional anchor, managing children's daily routines and providing consistent emotional support. Overall, the findings align with developmental theories which suggest that late adolescence is marked by improved emotional regulation, deeper empathy, and more balanced interpersonal interactions, including those within the family (Smetana, 2011). The narrowing standard deviations further suggest that as

students mature, their perceptions of the parent-child relationship become more uniform, pointing to greater emotional closeness and stability across the adolescent population.

4. Locality Wise Status of Parent-Child Relationship

The locality where a family lives can greatly affect the parent-child relationship. In areas with limited resources or challenging environments, parents and children might experience more stress, leading to weaker bonds (Leventhal & Brooks-Gunn, 2000). On the other hand, families in safer, well-resourced neighborhoods often have stronger connections because they benefit from better support and social networks (Furstenberg et al., 1999). In present study locality refers geographical area, i.e. hill and plain. Hill locality comprises secondary school students of Bhimtal block and Ramgarh block, while plain locality included secondary school students of Haldwani block and Kotabhag block.

Table 6 Locality wise status of Parent-Child Relationship among secondary school students (N=800)

	Hill (N=400)		Plain (N=400)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Father-child Relationship	265.85	26.58	266.93	27.03
Mother-child Relationship	270.46	26.24	272.43	26.93
Overall Parent-child Relationship	268.40	24.78	269.93	25.42

Figure 7 Locality wise status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students

Table 6 and Figure 7 show that the parent-child relationship scores for secondary school students are similar in hilly and plain regions. For the father-child relationship, the mean score for the hilly region is 265.85 (SD = 26.58), while the plain region has a slightly higher score of 266.93 (SD = 27.03). For the mother-child relationship, the mean score is 270.46 (SD = 26.24) in the hilly region and 272.43 (SD = 26.93) in the plain region. The overall parent-child relationship shows a mean of 268.40 (SD = 24.78) in the hilly region and 269.93 (SD = 25.42) in the plain region. These results indicate minimal differences between the two regions, with slightly higher mean scores in the plain locality. The similar standard deviations suggest comparable variability in both regions. Cultural factors like joint family systems and strong familial bonds in Uttarakhand likely contribute to these consistent patterns. The slight differences may be due to lifestyle, resource access, or parental occupations, but they do not significantly affect the parent-child relationship quality.

5 Status of Parent-Child Relationship with Respect to their Parent's Occupation:

Parent occupation significantly influences the parent-child relationship, affecting the caliber of time, resources, and emotional support provided to children. Studies suggested that parents in demanding or stressful occupations may have limited interaction with their children, which can impact the child's development and emotional well-being (Milkie et al., 2004). Conversely, parents in stable and flexible jobs are often more available, leading to stronger parent-child bonds and better developmental outcomes for children (Brooks-Gunn & Markman, 2005). Table 7 shows the status of parent-child relationship among respondents with respect to their father occupation. In present study father occupation is categorized into two categories i.e. government and non-government.

Table 7 Parent-Child Relationship Status Based on Father's Occupation :

	Government (N=212)		Non- Government(N=588)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Father-child Relationship	265.85	26.58	266.93	27.03
Mother-child Relationship	270.46	26.24	272.43	26.93
Overall Parent-child Relationship	268.40	24.78	269.93	25.42

Figure 8 Status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students with respect to their father's occupation

Table 7 and Figure 8 show similar parent-child relationship scores across government and non-government sectors. Students with government-employed parents had a mean score of 265.85 (SD = 26.58) for father-child relationships, while those with non-government-employed parents had a slightly higher mean of 266.93 (SD = 27.03). For mother-child relationships, the mean score was 270.46 (SD = 26.24) in the government sector and 272.43 (SD = 26.93) in the non-government sector. The overall parent-child relationship score was 268.40 (SD = 24.78) for the government sector and 269.93 (SD = 25.42) for the non-government sector.

These results show minimal differences, with slightly higher scores in the non-government sector. The similar standard deviations suggest that parental employment type does not significantly affect the parent-child relationship, indicating other familial or contextual factors may play a more prominent role.

A possible explanation lies in the occupational patterns typical of Uttarakhand, where many government employees—particularly in the armed forces, police, or teaching professions—often face

frequent transfers or remote postings, leading to extended periods away from their families. This physical distance may reduce opportunities for daily interaction and emotional bonding, particularly in the father-child relationship. Conversely, parents in the non-government sector—such as those engaged in agriculture, private jobs, or local businesses—are more likely to reside near their families, allowing for more frequent and consistent communication and engagement with their children. This proximity may contribute to the slightly higher relationship scores observed.

Table 8 Parent-Child Relationship Status Based on Mother's Occupation :

	Housewife(N=659)		Working(N=141)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Father-child Relationship	265.82	26.81	269.04	26.64
Mother-child Relationship	271.44	26.44	271.48	27.38
Overall Parent-child Relationship	268.88	25.08	270.50	25.22

Figure 9 Status of parent-child relationship among secondary school students with respect to their mother's occupation

Table 8 and Figure 9 show minimal differences in parent-child relationships based on mothers' occupational status. Respondents with housewives as mothers had a mean score of 265.82 (SD = 26.81) for father-child relationships, while those with working mothers had a slightly higher mean of 269.04 (SD = 26.64). For mother-child relationships, both groups had nearly identical scores: 271.44 (SD = 26.44) for housewives and 271.48 (SD = 27.38) for working mothers. The overall parent-child relationship score was 268.88 (SD = 25.08) for housewives and 270.50 (SD = 25.22) for working mothers.

These results indicate that the quality of parent-child relationships is largely consistent across both groups, with only slight variations in the mean scores. The similar standard deviations suggest that a mother's occupational status does not significantly affect relationship quality, implying that other factors may play a more important role.

Results of present study shows that the nature of parent-child interactions remains consistent regardless of whether fathers work in government or non-government sectors, or whether mothers are employed or stay-at-home. These findings suggested that the quality of parent-child relationships is influenced more by other factors, such as parenting practices, family dynamics, and communication styles, rather than the specific occupational roles of the parents. This underscores the importance of focusing on universal aspects of parenting to foster strong parent-child relationships across various occupational backgrounds. In contrast to present findings Agrawal (2020) found strong association with the working status of the mother and parent child relationship among secondary school students. According to results reported by Paulson et al. (1990), Sons felt a stronger bond with their fathers when their mothers were not working, whereas daughters' experienced closer relationships with both parents when their mothers were either not employed or working part-time.

7. Status of Parent-Child Relationship with Respect to their Parent's Education

The educational background of parents significantly influences the quality of the parent-child relationship. Davis-Kean (2005) and Spera (2005) reported that parents with higher education levels are more likely to engage in positive and supportive interactions with their children, fostering better communication, emotional support, and academic encouragement. McNeal (1999) also highlights that

such parents are more involved in their children's education, providing essential assets, guidance, and support that enhance cognitive and emotional development. In the present study, parental educational background is categorized into five groups: illiterate, high school, intermediate, graduate, and postgraduate. Table 4.9 presents the mean and standard deviation scores for the parent-child relationship based on the father's educational background.

Table 9 Parent-child relationship status based on father's educational background:

	Father's Educational Background	N	Mean	S.D.
Parent-child relationship	Illiterate	98	267.75	24.384
	High School	271	267.292	25.292
	Intermediate	175	270.337	24.897
	Graduate	137	269.197	26.107
	Post graduate	119	269.924	24.587

Table 9 presents data on the relationship between fathers' educational levels and parent-child relationship scores. The data show mean scores and standard deviations for respondents based on their fathers' education. The findings revealed that, the educational level of fathers has a limited effect on the quality of the parent-child relationship. The mean scores for the parent-child relationship are relatively similar across different educational backgrounds, with only minor variations. Specifically, the highest mean score is observed in the intermediate level category (270.337), while the lowest is in the illiterate category (267.75). Other educational levels fall in between, showing only slight differences. Standard deviations, which measure the variability of scores, are also quite consistent across all educational groups, ranging from 24.384 to 26.107. This consistency indicates that the variability in relationship quality is similar regardless of the father's education level. Results of present study revealed that, the educational level of the father does not significantly affect the quality of the parent-child relationship.

Table 10 Parent-child relationship status based on mother's educational background :

	Mother's Educational Background	N	Mean	S.D.
	Illiterate	98	266.102	24.384

Parent-child relationship	High School	271	269.162	25.292
	Intermediate	175	270.337	24.879
	Graduate	137	269.197	26.107
	Post graduate	119	269.924	24.587

Table 10 provides data on the relationship between mothers' educational levels and parent-child relationship scores. The data shows that, a mother's education level has a small effect on the parent-child relationship quality. The highest mean score is for children of mothers with an intermediate level of education (270.337), while the lowest is for children of illiterate mothers (266.102). Scores for other education levels are close to these figures. The consistency in standard deviations across all groups (24.384 to 26.107) indicates that the variability in relationship quality is similar regardless of the mother's education. Overall, higher maternal education is associated with slightly better parent-child relationship scores.

The limited effect of both mothers' and fathers' educational levels on the parent-child relationship could be attributed to several factors. Cultural and socioeconomic influences often play a more significant role in shaping family dynamics, where values, respect for authority, and traditional parenting practices might be more impactful than educational background. Emotional involvement and engagement, which are essential for strong parent-child bonds, are likely not influenced heavily by education. Both mothers and fathers, regardless of their educational levels, may prioritize similar aspects of parenting, such as providing emotional support and care, leading to comparable relationship quality. Moreover, factors like practical skills, emotional intelligence, and family structure may play a more prominent role than formal education in determining the quality of relationships. Socioeconomic status and parenting styles could also have a stronger influence on relationship dynamics, suggesting that various factors, rather than education alone, contribute to the quality of the parent-child bond.

Conclusion

The present study concludes that the majority of secondary school students in Nainital district experience an average level of parent-child relationship, with a relatively stronger emotional bond observed with mothers compared to fathers. Male respondents reported slightly better relationships with

both parents than female respondents. As adolescents grow older, their relationships with parents tend to become more stable and consistent, aligning with existing research that indicates maturity brings greater emotional understanding and bonding. Differences in parent-child relationships between students from hilly and plain regions were minimal, with students from plain areas reporting slightly better connections. The study also found that parents' occupational and educational backgrounds had limited impact on the quality of the parent-child relationship. This suggests that other factors, such as parenting practices, family dynamics, emotional communication, and the overall home environment, play a more significant role in shaping strong parent-child bonds.

Educational Implications

1. **Parenting Workshops:** Schools should organize regular parenting workshops to guide parents on effective parenting strategies, emotional communication, and understanding the developmental needs of adolescents.
2. **Strengthening Counseling Services:** School-based counseling programs should be enhanced to help students openly discuss family issues and receive appropriate emotional and psychological support.
3. **Encouraging Father Involvement:** As the study found stronger bonds with mothers, efforts must be made to actively encourage and involve fathers in the emotional and educational development of their children.
4. **Gender-Sensitive Approaches:** Educational institutions should adopt gender-sensitive strategies that address the different emotional needs and experiences of boys and girls in parent-child relationships.
5. **Context-Specific Interventions:** Although the differences between hilly and plain regions were minor, programs tailored to specific local challenges—especially in hilly areas—can help enhance parent-child communication and support systems.
6. **Empowering Teachers:** Teachers should be trained to recognize the influence of family dynamics on student behavior and learning. They can play a supportive role in bridging communication gaps between students and parents.
7. **Inclusive Peer Culture:**
An inclusive school environment should be cultivated where all students feel valued and respected, promoting a sense of belonging and reducing social exclusion.

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